

Some Observations on the Theory of Fluids and Ionic Assemblies

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THE exact molecular theory of liquids and liquid mixture still possess problems which make it difficult to apply it to actual problems of interest to chemists. These difficulties are accentuated in the assemblies in which interactions are mainly long range forces, e.g. by coulombic forces.

We in this laboratory have been trying to investigate certain features of this interesting problem. We take this opportunity to summarise some of our findings, a good number of which is yet unpublished.

The obvious starting point for all conjectures in this field is the relation

$$\frac{\partial f_h}{\partial t} + \sum_{i=1}^h \frac{\partial f_h}{\partial \mathbf{r}^{(i)}} \cdot \vec{\xi}^{(i)} + \sum_{i=1}^h \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi^{(i)}} \left(f_h \vec{\eta}^{(i)} \right) = 0$$

$$\text{with } \vec{\eta}^{(i)} = \frac{1}{f_h} \int \dots \int g_h \left[\eta^{(i)} \frac{h}{\parallel} \right] d\eta^{(i)} \quad (1)$$

where

f_h is h th order distribution function determining both velocity and position,

t is the time variable,

\vec{r}^i is the position vector describing the i th particle,

$\vec{\xi}^{(i)}$ is the velocity vector,

$\vec{\eta}^{(i)}$ is the acceleration vector, and

g_h is the rate of acceleration vector of its particle.

Equation (1) is exact, i.e. its derivation does not involve any serious physical approximations.

The assumption that the intermolecular potential energy may be written in terms of the sum of individual pair potentials $\phi(rs)$, i.e. as

$$\phi = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{r,s=1}^N \phi(rs) \quad (2)$$

reduces equation (1) to

$$\frac{\partial f_h}{\partial t} + \sum_{i=1}^h \frac{\partial f_h}{\partial \mathbf{r}^{(i)}} \cdot \vec{\xi}^{(i)} = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i,j=1}^h \frac{\partial f_h}{\partial \xi^{(i)}} \cdot \frac{\partial \phi^{(i,j)}}{\partial \mathbf{r}^{(i)}}$$

$$+ \frac{1}{m} \int \int \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{\partial \phi^{(i,h+1)}}{\partial \mathbf{r}^i} \cdot \frac{\partial f_{h+1}}{\partial \xi^{(i)}} \frac{\partial}{\partial \mathbf{r}^{(h+1)}} \cdot \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi^{(h+1)}} \quad (3)$$

Equation (3) has by now come to be regarded as the BGYK Equation to denote multiple authorship of this equation by Begoliubor², Born³ and Green¹, Yvon³ and Kirkwood^{4,5}.

Born and Green¹ have shown that under rather restrictive conditions this equation for $h=2$ may be reduced to the Boltzman integrodifferential equation from which the theories of transport phenomena of dilute gases start.

Again, the Equation (4) reduces to (1), (3), (4)

$$\frac{\partial \eta_h}{\partial t} + \sum_j \frac{n_h}{kT} \frac{\partial \phi^{(i,j)}}{\partial \mathbf{r}^{(i)}} + \int \frac{n_{h+1}}{kT} \frac{\partial \phi^{(i,h+1)}}{\partial \mathbf{r}^{(i)}} \cdot \frac{\partial}{\partial \mathbf{r}^{(h+1)}} \quad (4)$$

where n_h is the h th order position distribution function.

We shall call equation (4) as the BGYK equilibrium equation. For $h=2$, the now famous approximation known as the superposition approximation.

$$\eta_3 \left(\vec{r}_1, \vec{r}_2, \vec{r}_3 \right) = \eta_2 \left(\vec{r}_1, \vec{r}_2 \right) \eta_2 \left(\vec{r}_2, \vec{r}_3 \right) \eta_2 \left(\vec{r}_1, \vec{r}_3 \right) \quad (5)$$

reduces the equation (4) after some manipulation to the Born Green equation :

$$\ln \frac{n_2(r)}{n^2} + \frac{\phi(r)}{kT} = \frac{\pi}{n^3} \int_0^{\infty} \int_{-s}^s (s^2 - t^2) \frac{(t+r)}{r} \left\{ n_2(t+r) - n^2 \right\} dt \quad (6)$$

$$n_2(s) \phi'(s) dr$$

Relations equivalent to the above were also proposed by Kirkwood and by Yvon.

Equation of State in terms of power series of I/V may be deduced from equation (6). It has been found that the second and the third virial coefficient calculated from $n_2(r)$ through the equation (6) above agree with the cluster integral formulations of imperfect gases as developed by Ursell⁷ and later perfected by Mayer and his associates^{8,9}, while the higher virial coefficients calculated from two theories differ. The coupled infinite set of integrodifferential equations (4) as such has never been studied earlier.

Elimination of superposition approximation by iterative procedure :

Since the cluster integral formulation is exact except for the assumption (2), we posed ourselves two problems :

(1) Could we devise some method of solving equation set (4) which does not involve superposition approximation (5), and

(2) Do all the virial coefficients calculated from equation set (4) agree with those obtained from the cluster integral theory ?

We did obtain definite answers to both these problems. We could devise (Guha¹⁰) two methods of solution of equation (4) itself. Both these methods are iterative methods. The first method started with the assumption that the zeroeth approximation to $n_h(r)$ is

$$n_{(h)}^0(r, \dots) = n^h \exp - \frac{1}{kT} \phi(\vec{r}_h) \quad (8)$$

We recognise, this approximation as it is, yield the correct value of the second virial coefficient. The correct value of the third virial coefficient can now be obtained by a single iterative step, the fourth by two iterative steps and so on. The results

incidentally prove the point (2) above, and we could regard the representation of a molecular assembly by the infinite set of the coupled integral equations (4) to be absolutely equivalent to the cluster integral formulations of the imperfect gases.

However, it has been shown that the equation of state derived by the cluster integral expansion of the partition function diverges in case of liquids. This makes the above procedure useless for the study of this state. Consequently, we have to find out a method which would possibly be of use of liquids. To achieve this end, we have observed that we can generalise Born and Green's result viz., the equation (6), has the approximate solution¹²

$$\eta_2(r) \approx n^2 e^{-\phi(r)/kT} \left\{ 1 + f(r) \right\}$$

$$\text{where } rf(r) = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^{\frac{1}{2}}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{\epsilon^2 s \beta^2(s) e^{irs}}{\lambda - \epsilon \beta(s)} ds \quad (9)$$

where ϵ is approximately equals 1, $\beta(s)$ is the Fourier transform of $(\exp. -\phi(r)/kT - 1)$ and $\lambda^{-1} = (2\pi)^{3/2} n$.

This expression can be expanded for low densities in a series which corresponds to (within the limitation of superposition approximation) the equation of state in power series of V^{-1} , similar to the one obtained from the cluster integral formulation. The latter is, as we have observed is divergent for high densities. On the other hand, one could expand it to another series which does not diverge for high densities characteristic of the liquid state. This result enables us to choose the zeroeth approximation for an iterative computation as

$$n_{(h)}^0 = n^h \exp - \frac{1}{kT} \left\{ \phi(\vec{r}_h) + f_{(h)}^0 \right\}$$

$$f_{(h)}^0 = f_{(h, h+1)}^0 + \sum_{i < h} f_{(ih)}^0 + f_{i, h+1}$$

$$\frac{n_{(h+1)}^0}{n_{(h)}^0} = n \exp - \frac{1}{kT} \left\{ \phi(\vec{r}_{(h+1)}) - \phi(\vec{r}_h) \right\} + \Delta f_{(h+1)}^0$$

$$\Delta f_{(h+1)}^0 = f_{(h+1)}^0 - f_{(h)}^0$$

and $f_{ih} =$

$$\frac{1}{(2\pi)^{\frac{1}{2}}} \frac{1}{r_{ih}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{\epsilon(r_{ih, h+1}) \beta^2(r_{ih, h+1}) e^{i(r_{ih}, r_{h, h+1})}}{\lambda - \epsilon \beta(r_{ih, h+1})} dr_{ih, h+1} \quad (10)$$

and we can derive the expression for $f_h(r)$ correct to any order of approximation, only by repetitive iterations. The meaning of different terms occurring in (10) are analogous to those in equation (9).

Expressions obtained by the above procedure are obviously valid both for liquid and gaseous state.

Intermolecular potential energy functions :

It is evident that the theory needs an *a priori* knowledge of the intermolecular potential energy function which can only be calculated through very involved quantum mechanical considerations. The prohibitive labour involved has so far precluded the detailed calculations but for any but a few insignificant cases. The other alternative is to use some expression. A familiar example for such a function is the Lennard-Jones function.

Since $g(r)$ is connected to $n_2(r)$ by the relation

$$g(r) = \frac{1}{n^2} n_2(r) \quad (11)$$

and since this function is connected to the X-ray scattering intensity function by

$$g(r) = 1 + 2\pi \int_0^{\infty} \left[\frac{I}{I_{of}} - 1 \right] r^2 dr \quad (12)$$

we may regard $g(r)$ as an experimental function. We asked ourselves whether we could invert the coupled equation set (4) to find out $\phi(r)$ from this experimental $g(r)$. We could in fact succeed in developing an iterative procedure for this purpose and applied this procedure to liquid Argon^(13,14).

Similar calculations were earlier performed by using numerical computations by digital computers by Johnson and March¹⁵ but for the starting point of their calculations they chose the much more approximate equation (6) rather than the equation set (4). We may note that since the latter equation set is not limited by the superposition approximation, our iterative procedure is a distinct improvement.

Subsequent calculations of $\phi(r)$ by liquid metals using their method, Johnson, Hutchinson and March¹⁶ observed long range oscillatory nature of the potentials for metal-metal interactions in liquid metals. We have ourselves also obtained similar results with our method. Our most interesting finding is interacting, however, the results of the computation of $\phi(r)$ for the interacting ions in the aqueous solutions

of NH_4Cl , NH_4Br , NH_4I . We observed that in none of the cases, the resulting $\phi(r)$ could be regarded as the simple superposition of coulombic potentials.

The above results indicate that the commonly used semiempirical $\phi(r)$ may not represent true state of affairs for intermolecular interactions in liquids. Since $g(r)$ is an experimentally determinable function, our calculations for $\phi(r)$ may be regarded as experimental determination of the potential energy function. Another pertinent observation we have made is that these "experimental" molecular potentials invariably show a temperature dependence, an observation which is contradictory to the properties which we can intuitively assign to the interaction of an isolated pair of molecules.

The last observation as we shall see later, appears to be very important in resolving the behaviour of long range intermolecular interactions.

Theoretical computations of different liquid properties

The usual procedure utilised for the most applications is to solve the integrodifferential equation (6) for $n_2(r)$ and use the resulting $n_2(r)$ for further calculations. We pointed out before that $n_2(r)$ could itself be regarded as an experimentally determinable quantity. One wonders that we may perhaps use these experimental $n_2(r)$ for calculation of the various properties of liquid. Such calculations would not be restricted by the superposition approximations and thus may provide some advantage in the understanding of the liquid state.

For most cases we need *a priori* of the knowledge of $\phi(r)$. Two procedures are open to us, one may calculate $\phi(r)$ from $n_2(r)$ by the method we have already described, or we may choose an empirical form of $\phi(r)$. Even though the first procedure would be more logical one, we have used the second procedure. Since $n_2(r)$ was obtainable as numerical tables, somewhat lengthy numerical computations were necessary in each case.

The relevant expressions for the different thermodynamical properties of liquids are¹⁸

$$E = \text{Internal Energy} = \frac{3}{2}NkT + 2\pi v \int_0^{\infty} n_2(r) \phi'(r) r^2 dr$$

$$P = \text{Pressure} = \frac{NkT}{V} - \frac{2\pi}{5} \int_0^{\infty} n_2(r) \phi'(r) r^3 dr$$

$$\mu = \text{Viscosity} = \frac{2\pi}{15} \left(\frac{m}{kT} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \int_0^{\infty} n_2(r) \phi'(r) r^2 dr$$

$$\gamma = \text{Surface tension} = \frac{\pi}{8} \int_0^{\infty} n_2(r) \phi'(r) r^4 dr \quad (13)$$

where $N/V =$ Number density $= n$

$m =$ atomic mass

$k =$ Boltzmann constant

$T =$ Temperature in $^{\circ}K$.

We (Sengupta and Guha¹⁹) calculated the surface tension and viscosity of several metals and alloys. The potential energy function chosen for calculation was Lennard-Jones potential. The results agreed well with the experiments.

Two other important properties of liquid state are the shear modulus of elasticity and the relaxation time. Using Buckingham exp-6 and Lennard Jones 6-9 potentials Guha and Lin²⁰ have calculated the shear and bulk modules of elasticity from the following equation,

$G_{\infty} =$ Shear modulus of elasticity $=$

$$\rho kT + \frac{2\pi\rho^2}{15} \int_0^{\infty} dr g(r) \frac{d}{dr} \left(r^4 \frac{d\phi}{dr} \right)$$

$K_{\infty} =$ Bulk modulus of elasticity $=$

$$\frac{2}{3}\rho kT + \frac{2\pi\rho^2}{9} \int_0^{\infty} dr g(r) r^2 \frac{d}{dr} \left(r \frac{d\phi}{dr} \right) \quad \dots 14$$

The results are reasonable. The relaxation time is related to elasticity by Maxwell's well known relation

$$\tau = \text{relaxation time} = \frac{\eta_s}{G_{\infty}}$$

where $\eta_s =$ shear viscosity.

This relation enabled us (Sengupta, Munshi and Guha²²) to calculate the relaxation time of liquid Argon at different temperatures near the melting point. Dasanacharya and Rao²³ had experimentally determined the relaxation time of liquid argon using the slow neutron scattering method, and found that τ was of the order 10^{-13} sec. and independent of temperature. Our calculations pointed out that the relaxation time is in general dependent on the temperature.

Another liquid property we (Sengupta, Bhattacharyya and Guha²³) have chosen is a transport property viz., the self diffusion coefficient. This property can also be related to the pair distribution functions. Rice and Allnat²⁴ have shown that the friction coefficient can be divided into two parts—one is the soft core part and the other is the hard core one.

$$\tau = \tau_s + \tau_H$$

where

$$\tau_H = \frac{8}{3} \rho^2 g(\sigma) (\pi m k T)^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

$$\tau_s = - \frac{\rho}{12\pi^2} \left(\frac{\pi m}{kT} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \int_0^{\infty} k^3 \tilde{u}_s(k) \tilde{G}(k) dk \quad (15)$$

where

$g_2(\sigma) =$ Radial distribution function at $r = \sigma$, where σ is the distance of closest approach of the molecules ;

$\tilde{u}_s(k) =$ Fourier transform of the long range part of the potential.

$\tilde{G}(k) =$ Fourier transform of $[g_2(R) - 1]$ with $g_2(R) =$ Pair correlation functions.

The other terms have usual meaning. They used the above relations to calculate the self diffusion coefficient of liquid argon. We²⁴ made similar calculation for the self diffusion coefficient of a number of metals viz., Na, K, Ru, Cs and Li. Our results agree well with the experimental values of Rahman²⁵ and others.

Some observations in the electrolyte theory :

One of the most important, at the same time the most baffling molecular assembly is the aqueous solution of an electrolyte. Here the intermolecular interactions are mainly coulombic.

There exists the celebrated formalism of Debye and Huckel devised to study this system. It correctly predicts the behaviour in the limiting case of infinite dilutions, however, attempts to extend it to more concentrated limits have largely been unsuccessful.

The usual theories of dense gases and fluids are supposed to be inadequate to tackle the coulombic interactions because the assumption (2) is not applicable. However, in the hands of Mayer and his associates (cf. Friedman²⁶ for an excellent summary), the cluster integral formalism for ionic assemblies has reached its culmination, and this formalism also presupposes assumption (2). From these theories also one obtains the same limiting law as the one predicted by Debye and Huckel theory. It is apparent, therefore, that the two theories are practically identical.

Fowler²⁸ long ago analysed the mathematical basis of Debye Huckel theory and came to the conclusion that the later theory is formally identical with the usual theories of imperfect gases. The only difference is that it implicitly introduces an extra assumption, the "superposition" approximation

$$W_{\alpha\beta} = Z_{\alpha}|e|\psi_{\beta}$$

where ψ_{β} average electrostatic potential at the site of particle β (16)
and $Z_{\alpha}|e|$ is the charge of particle α .

This approximation introduces an inherent inconsistency in the Debye Huckel theory. Obviously the correct relation would be $W_{\alpha\beta} = \rho_{\alpha}\psi_{\beta}$ (17)

where, ρ_{α} is the effective average charge at the position of particle.

We in this laboratory wanted to see whether the replacement of the "superposition approximation"

of Debye and Fowler by equation (17) makes the theory more realistic. Bhattacharyya²⁸ made detailed calculations and found out the actual changes brought about in the final results by the replacement of the superposition approximation to direct calculations is small and do not account for the peculiarities of the electrolyte behaviour.

We then thought that these peculiarities could result from another fact, viz., the basic difference that actually exists between the imperfect gaseous state and the liquids—which was pointed out by Born and Fuchs¹¹. Bhattacharyya²⁸ re-examined the calculations of Moollen²⁹ who formulated electrolyte theory on the basis of Born Green equation (4). Bhattacharyya studied the solutions similar to those obtained by Born and Green¹² which would be valid for liquid state. It was observed, however, that again the resulting corrections do not adequately explain the electrolyte characteristics.

The answer to the problem, therefore, must exist elsewhere. One may naturally assume that the solvent ion interactions are the main controlling factors. However, for incorporation of such interaction we have to go deeper into the theory. However, even before we attempt to formulate the theory to incorporate ion-solvent interactions, we may recall the fact already mentioned earlier, that in contrast to usual belief the Debye Huckel theory does not provide a better prescription for long range interaction than the usual imperfect gas formation. We have thus to discover first such a prescription.

Even in the case of ordinary molecular assemblies equation (2) may be inadequate. This is evident from our calculations of experimental intermolecular potential energies. As stated above, we have always found them to be temperature dependent. This is a paradoxical situation, because according to the usual meaning of $\phi(r)$, these should be independent of temperature.

We may notice that instead of the assumption (2), if we write

$$\bar{\phi} = \sum_{i \neq j} \bar{\phi}_{ij} \quad (18)$$

where, $\bar{\phi}$ is the potential energy averaged for all molecules, except for a given pair. Needless to say that $\bar{\phi}_{ij}$ is temperature dependant although ϕ is not.

This equation is exact. With this relation BDGYK equation can still be derived. The only change is that ϕ has to be replaced by the average. The BGYK equation (5) also survives, subject to this change.

The equations can now be solved only by iterative procedures after taking the solutions obtained as usual by approximation (2) as the first order approximation.

Actual calculations³³ to second approximation reveal changes in the coefficient in $\frac{1}{V^3}$ term i.e. in the fourth virial coefficient term in the equation of state of the low density region. This term, we may note, is of the same order as the error introduced by BGYK superposition approximation (equation 5). For coulombic interaction this term is rather large.

We, therefore, surmise that the observation that equation (18) must replace the approximate relation (2), may provide the key towards the solution of the problems of long range interactions. Because, the deviations from equation (2) may then be actually computed by successive iterations.

A very large number of papers have been published recently on liquids, imperfect gases and ionic assemblies. We have here referred to only those which have direct bearings with the line of reasoning we have followed.

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